

Studies on Adsorption Indicators*. Mono- and Bis-hydroxyphenyl Phthalides as Adsorption Indicators in Argentometric Titrations of Bromide and Thiocyanate Ions

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PHENOLPHTHALEIN has been highly recommended in literature by Uzumasa¹, Mehrotra², and Akiyama and Yabe³ as an adsorption indicator in slightly alkaline condition for the argentometric titration of iodide, chloride and thiocyanate ions respectively.

In the present communication phenolphthalein (VIII) and 7 new phenol dyes (I-VII) have been studied for their utility as adsorption indicators. The dyes (I-VII) being: 3-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)phthalide(I), 3,3-bis(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide(II), 3-acetyl-3-(*o*- or *p*-hydroxyphenyl)-4,5,6,7-tetrachlorophthalide(III), 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-4,5-dimethoxyphthalide(IV), 3-phenyl-3-(*o*- or *p*-hydroxyphenyl) 2, 3-naphthalide (V), β -1-naphthyl-phenolsuccinein(VI), β -2-naphthyl-phenol-succinein(VII) and phenolphthalein(VIII).

Experimental

Material: AgNO₃, KBr were A.R.(BDH) and KSCN was I.R.(BDH) grade reagents.

Indicator Solutions, Preparation of dyes⁴.

Procedure: AgNO₃ from the burette is added slowly, shaking the contents of the conical flask all the time. Complete coagulation leaving the clear supernatant liquid occurs exactly at the equivalence point.

Results and Discussion

The dye 3-(*p*-hydroxyphenyl)phthalide(I) is in some respects better than phenolphthalein(VIII) and can be used in neutral as well as in slightly alkaline condition for bromide ions (0.1–0.005 N solutions) and thiocyanate ions (0.1–0.01 N solutions). Rest of the dyes (II-VIII) can only be used in slightly alkaline condition. Thus, for bromide ions (VIII) and II can be used for 0.1–0.005 N solutions; dyes (III-V) for solutions 0.1–0.02 N) and for thiocyanate ions (dye II can be used for solutions 0.1–0.005 N; dyes I, IV and V for solutions 0.1–0.01 N; III can be used well for 0.1 N solution). Dyes VI and VII are unsuitable.

Detailed studies of I, II, III, IV, V and VIII have been shown in the given Tables.

TABLE—1 DYES I, VIII AND II USED AS ADSORPTION INDICATORS (FOR THE ESTIMATION OF BROMIDE IONS. CONC. OF AgNO₃ USED: SAME AS KBr, VOL. REQD. 10 ml IN EACH CASE. DYE I HAS BEEN USED IN NEUTRAL AS WELL AS IN SLIGHTLY ALKALINE CONDITION; AND DYES VIII AND II IN SLIGHTLY ALKALINE CONDITION ONLY.

Dye	Concn.	Drops of KBr indicator	Transition of colour	Remarks
I	0.1 N	6	yellow suspn.→orange-pink ppt.	(a)
I	0.02 N	6	yellowish-white suspn.→orange ppt.	(a)
I	0.01 N	5	orange-yellow turbidity→orange ppt.	(a)
I	0.005 N	4	orange-yellow turbidity→orange ppt.	(a)
VIII	0.1 N	6	pink tinged-white suspn.→pink ppt.	(b)
VIII	0.02 N	6	pink tinged-white suspn.→violet-blue ppt.	(b)
VIII	0.005 N	4	white suspn.→greenish-ash ppt.	(b)
II	0.1 N	6	yellowish-white suspn.→violet-ash ppt.	(b)
II	0.02 N	6	yellowish-white suspn.→violet-ash ppt.	(b)
II	0.01 N	5	white suspn.→bluish-violet-ash ppt.	(b)
II	0.005 N	3	violet shaded turbidity→light green ppt.	(b)

(a)=complete coagulation and clear supernatant liquid at the end point.

(b)=complete coagulation and faint pink supernatant liquid at the end point.

TABLE—2 DYES (I-V) USED AS ADSORPTION INDICATORS FOR THE ESTIMATION OF SCN⁻. CONC. OF AgNO₃ USED: SAME AS KSCN, VOL. REQD. 10 ml IN EACH CASE. CONDITIONS OF TITRATIONS SAME AS MENTIONED IN TABLE 1.

Dye	Concn.	Drops of KSCN	Transition of colour	Remarks
I	0.1 N	8	orange tinged-white suspn.→orange-pink ppt.	(a)
I	0.02 N	5	white suspn.→orange-pink ppt.	(a)
I	0.01 N	5	orange tinged-white suspn.→orange-pink ppt.	(a)
II	0.1 N	8	white suspn.→violet ppt.	(a)
II	0.02 N	8	white suspn.→violet ppt.	(a)
II	0.01 N	5	violet tinged-white suspn.→violet ppt.	(a)
II	0.005 N	4	violet-white turbid soln.→violet ppt.	(b)
III	0.1 N	8	white suspn.→violet ppt.	(a)
IV	0.1 N	9	violet tinged-white suspn.→violet ppt.	(a)
IV	0.02 N	8	violet-white suspn.→violet ppt.	(a)
IV	0.01 N	6	violet shaded suspn.→violet ppt.	(b)
V	0.1 N	10	white suspn.→violet ppt.	(a)
V	0.01 N	6	white suspn.→orange-violet ppt.	(a)

(a)=immediate coagulation; at the end point a through light colour develops in the solution like that of the ppt. coagulated, and leaves a clear supernatant liquid.

(b)=delayed coagulation; end point colour change same as mentioned under (a).

The following points emerge on comparing the above dyes (I–V) with Phenolphthalein:

1. That the dye II is far better than phenolphthalein in slightly alkaline condition for (0.1–0.005 N) solutions while phenolphthalein can only be used for 0.1–0.01 N thiocyanate solutions.

2. That the dye I has the advantage of its being used as an indicator in neutral as well as slightly alkaline condition (for Br⁻, 0.1–0.005 N; for SCN⁻, 0.1–0.01 N).

3. That the dyes (III–V) can be used for solutions of higher concentrations in slightly alkaline condition ranging in dilution from 0.1–0.01 N.

4. That the dyes VI and VII are unsuitable for the titrations of bromide and thiocyanate ions.

* Part I & II, See *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (1976), 53, 848–951

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Chemical Examination of Flowers of *Asparagus gonocladus* Baker

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ASPARAGUS gonocladus, Baker¹ (N.O. Liliaceae) known as Shakakul in Hindi is used in the indigenous system of medicine for various ailments. Previous studies have shown the presence of asparagine¹ in other species.

The fresh flowers were repeatedly extracted in the cold with successive quantities of methanolic hydrochloric acid (1%). The red coloured combined extract so obtained responded to colour tests for the presence of anthocyanins². Paper chromatographic examination revealed the presence of only one anthocyanin which was crystallised from a mixture of acetone and ether as red crystals, C₂₉H₃₅O₁₇Cl, m.p. 165°(d), λ_{max}530 nm, ν_{max}^{Nujol} 3380, 1638, 1555, 1498, 1460, 1432, 1346, 1180, 1042, 932, 910, 886, 820, ..., etc. cm⁻¹. The compound on hydrolysis with 7 per cent. sulphuric acid yielded Malvidine chloride, C₁₇H₁₅O₇Cl, m.p. above 300°, λ_{max}542 nm, ν_{max}^{Nujol} 1640, 1550, 1500, 1464, 1430, 1350, 1170, 1040, ..., etc. cm⁻¹, and glucose (identified by co-chromatography with the authentic sample and osazone formation). The quantitative estimation of sugar moiety by colorimetric method³ showed the presence of glucose and Malvidine chloride in the molar ratio of 2 : 1. The anthocyanin was identified to be Malvin chloride by mixed m.p. with the authentic sample.

The flowers were washed with ethanol and then exhaustively extracted with 80 per cent. ethanol. The ethanolic extract responded to colour test with ninhydrin for the presence of amino acids. Paper chromatographic examination revealed the presence of an amino acid. Its identity was confirmed by co-chromatography with the authentic sample of asparagine.

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Carboxylation of Pyrazolones and Application of the Products

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IN continuation of our reports on heterocyclic fungicides¹⁻⁴, in which it has been noted that 2-pyrazolin-5-one derivatives possess significant fungicidal activity against the rice blast fungus *Pyricularia Oryzae*, we have tried to synthesise some water soluble carboxy derivatives of 2-pyrazolin-5-ones herein, for their application as systemic fungicides. A compound, to behave as a systemic fungicide must have high water solubility in order to be absorbed by the rice plant from the soil. It has been observed that carboxylation of 2-pyrazolin-5-one nucleus renders it more water soluble.

It had been reported⁵ that carboxylation of resorcinol can be effected by heating in water with potassium bicarbonate at 100°. As 2-pyrazolin-5-one nucleus has marked similarity with phenolic compounds, the same method is applied here to carboxylate 1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one and 3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one.

Six carboxy acids were prepared and screened for antifungal activity against the fungus *P. Oryzae* by the standard method⁶. The details of the observations on these compounds are given in Table 1. It has been observed that all these compounds except compound No. 4, exhibited more fungicidal activity than the corresponding compounds without the carboxy groups. Fungicidal activity of all these later compounds have been reported earlier^{1,8}.

Amongst these, compounds 2 and 5 are found to be the most effective potential systemic fungicides,